

EXPLORING CLIMATE ANXIETY: INFLUENCE OF NEW MEDIA AND MENTAL HEALTH

MOHAMMAD ZAID OBAIDAT

Assistant Professor, Journalism and Communication Technology, Faculty of Media, Department of Media and Communication Technology, Jadara University. Email: M.obaidat@jadara.edu.jo

JAHAR MALAL

Fatima Jinnah Women University.

AYESHA QAMAR

Fatima Jinnah Women University.

MOHAMMAD HABES

Radio & TV Department, Yarmouk University, Jordan.

Abstract

Our research paper reviews existing literature on climate anxiety, with a particular focus on what's its status in Pakistan. Climate anxiety, which involves fear and distress related to climate change, is becoming an increasing concern worldwide. It examines the extent of climate anxiety in Pakistan and explores how exposure to media coverage of climate-related events may influence it. This review looks at current research trends on climate anxiety, including its definition, effects on mental health, and the role of media in shaping public views. The findings of our study reveal significant differences in how climate anxiety is defined and measured across various studies. We also observed that climate anxiety literature lacks a qualitative perspective. We emphasize the importance of developing a clearer and more uniform understanding of climate anxiety to improve research on the topic. It also highlighted the role of media in influencing anxiety levels, particularly in countries like Pakistan where climate-related disasters are common. The paper concludes by encouraging more research on climate anxiety in Pakistan, especially qualitative studies.

Keywords: Climate Anxiety, Eco-Anxiety, Climate Stress.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has recently become a critical issue that impacts every aspect of life. In the past, debates were about climate change and there were significant divisions in public opinion. There were questions about whether climate change was even real or not. However, as climate-related disasters have become more frequent and severe, the reality of climate change is now accepted by the majority (Anne, Goda Perlaviciute, & Steg, 2023). By 2025, most of the population knows this 'warming of climate system' is affecting them. Significant international efforts, such as those led by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the annual Conference of the Parties (e.g., COP28), are being organized to address this 'shared' challenge, indicating acknowledgment of the current state. (Dechezleprêtre et al., 2022). The impact of climate change is far beyond environmental concerns. Whitmarsh et al. (2022) highlight its significant effects on human well-being. It encompasses mental, emotional, and social angles. Recent literature has

included physical and financial consequences as well as mental impacts on people. Our research continues to examine this trend in Pakistan. This paper systematically reviews literature exploring the reality of climate anxiety and its connection to media exposure. Our research is important because it highlights the need to focus on climate change-associated research in Pakistan. It will help news organizations, journalists, and policymakers consider impacts on mental health as well while curating content for climate change awareness. They need to be careful when framing the news as a disaster only, as this can lead to responses such as anxiety and stress. We recommend our fellow researchers and students do more research on the framing of climate change news in Pakistan and worldwide.

Climate anxiety is often referred to with a negative connotation. According to Clayton and Karazsia (2020), climate anxiety is defined as the negative emotional reactions of people to the news of climate change and related disasters. This can be due to suffering directly due to a disaster i.e., by being a victim of damages caused by a storm or flood, or due to being subsequently displaced. As Scher (2018) defines climate anxiety, this suffering is a growing emotional toll of climate change. This condition of fear and stress is called eco-anxiety or more specifically climate anxiety. There is growing evidence in scholarly literature that people may also suffer climate anxiety without having direct exposure to any disaster. It happens due to increasing awareness about the topic of climate change which may result in mental stress. There are also some reports on the relationship between media reporting of climate change and growing cases of climate anxiety.

While there are certain reports on climate anxiety (or climate depression in some articles) in the US, UK, and some European countries, there has been less focus on the condition of the Global South. We believe that it is important to understand the reaction of people of Global South specifically because countries of Global South are the least contributors towards climate change, yet fall among the top victims of climate disasters (Ittefaq et al., 2023). A nexus of factors including the misinformation and inexperience of climate journalism contributes to increasing climate-related stress in under-developed countries like Pakistan (Ejaz, Muhammad Ittefaq, & Arif, 2024). According to these authors' research, journalists cited a lack of education and expertise as significant barriers to effective environmental reporting. This is the reason that researchers from Pakistan have recently started to focus on climate change reporting trends. However, very few researchers have come out to address the topic in the last few years. Ejaz, Ittefaq, and Jamil (2023) demonstrated that there is a dire need to have scholarly research regarding climate change reporting and how to improve it. Our research fills this gap by systematically reviewing climate anxiety and relating it to the Pakistani context.

Research questions

The psychological response to the news of climate disasters, known as climate anxiety or more specifically climate change anxiety, is particularly relevant in Pakistan. This is because, in Pakistan, people have faced intense physical, health, and financial damage caused by climate disasters. This scenario raises concerns for the mental health of

Pakistani people. People of Pakistan may also be suffering from similar climate anxiety as people of other parts of the world suffer. This discussion leads to research questions for this research:

Is there a presence of climate anxiety in Pakistan? If so, how is it manifesting within the population? Furthermore, how does media exposure to climate-related news influence climate anxiety among individuals?

Research objectives

- To determine whether climate anxiety is present in the population of Pakistan
- To investigate the relationship between media exposure to climate-related news

Literature Review

What is climate anxiety?

Climate anxiety is becoming a major concern in mental health and behavioral studies. People's emotional reactions to global climate change often include concern, worry, anxiety, and terror. This state of fear is referred to as climate anxiety (Boluda-Verdú, Senent-Valero, Casas-Escolano, Matijasevich, & Pastor-Valero, 2022). People are increasingly worried about the impact of climate change on their lives. Before we proceed towards more new terms, it is important to understand climate change. According to UNFCC (2023), climate change is defined as a change in climate that is caused directly or indirectly due to human activity and modifies the composition of the global atmosphere, in addition to natural climatic instability observed over a long period.

Rising temperatures, extreme weather events, and environmental threats worry the public's safety, health, and livelihoods (Clayton et al., 2017). Clayton's research shows that climate anxiety deeply affects mental health, leading to fear and a condition of stress. People exposed to repeated climate disasters face higher risks of chronic stress, leading to a state of climate anxiety (Cianconi, Betrò, & Janiri, 2020). To express a sense of loss and pain, some scholars have also used the term 'climate depression'. However, a group of scholars have advised to avoid using 'medicalized' terms in climate research (Budziszewska & Kałwak, 2022). As a part of our findings, we have explored in detail this terminological tussle later in the article.

Pro-environmental Behavior: Does Climate Anxiety Drive Action?

If someone is concerned about a particular situation, it seems logical that they would take action to change it. However, when it comes to climate change, the situation is not that simple. Many people experience stress and anxiety related to climate change. This does not always translate into taking action to address the issue (Lamm, McCann, & Howe, 2022).

Research on the connection between climate anxiety and action shows mixed results. On one hand, some individuals channel their concerns into positive actions, such as recycling, reducing their carbon footprint, or joining activist campaigns (Ojala, Cunsolo,

Ogunbode, & Middleton, 2021). On the other hand, some people feel so overwhelmed by the climate crisis that they avoid taking meaningful steps altogether. This sense of helplessness can lead to inaction, despite the deep concern they may feel.

In countries like Pakistan, the relationship between climate anxiety and action is even less clear. Limited resources, lack of awareness, and inadequate infrastructure make it harder for individuals to translate their concerns into actions. As highlighted by Ullah, (2025) et al., a real-life example is the 2022 floods in Pakistan. The floods displaced millions and caused widespread destruction. Such floods are an example of a lack of preparedness in case of such a crisis. People expressed concerns but often lacked the tools or systems to take effective and preventive actions. Hence, the present situation emphasizes the need for more research aligning with how climate stress can be materialized into pro-environmental actions to benefit everyone.

Impact on Mental Health

The relation between extreme weather events and deteriorating mental health state has been proved by many researchers. One of such research is done by Ojala, Cunsolo, Ogunbode, and Middleton (2021). They say that climate disasters, like floods and droughts, increase feelings of stress. Similarly, Lawrance, Thompson, Newberry Le Vay, Page, and Jennings (2022) conclude in their research that climate change associates stress as a part of the bigger problem of climate change. To fight the challenges posed by climate change, we must consider the impacts on mental health as well (Cianconi, Betrò, & Janiri, 2020). There are two types of mental stress conditions mentioned in the literature. One is **clinically diagnosable**; the other **non-clinical** one is a state of fear and anxiety due to climatic conditions. This point has been discussed in detail in the findings section of this paper.

In Pakistan, the 2022 floods displaced millions of people. Many of them still struggle with mild to severe trauma and a lack of mental health support (Akram & Mushtaq, 2024). This is because the victims of floods experienced the climatic disaster in person as well as their means of living were directly affected. Experiencing climate disasters directly makes anxiety worse. Events like floods or heatwaves leave people feeling helpless and unsafe. In Pakistan, displaced people face severe trauma, along with losing their homes, jobs, and communities. Hence, there is a dire need to study how to tackle the climatic problem in a broader sense.

Theoretical Intervention: Media and Climate Anxiety

Being a systematic literature review, we haven't applied directly any theory. However, we sought theoretical support to locate our idea of research from three theories. First is cultivation theory, second is the mediatization process and third is nudge theory. The guidance about theories is taken from the relevant literature.

1. **Cultivation theory:** Media plays a significant role in shaping public perceptions of climate change. This aligns with George Gerbner's cultivation theory (Gerbner, 1976). Gerbner suggested that prolonged exposure to violent content on television could

make viewers more violent. According to this theory, people who consume more media think about the world the same way the media has portrayed it. Gerbner researched by showing violent content and observed a similar sentiment expressed in the viewer's behavior. Because the media often portrays the world as dangerous, people usually perceive it similarly.

While Gerbner's main focus was on violent television content, the same principle has been applied to other media narratives. Applying the same idea in this research, we have proposed that watching climatic news heightens people's anxiety as they start thinking of climate change as an urgent threat. This is because the media usually frames climate change events as disastrous (Painter, 2022). Our proposition is based on the research of Andersen, Djerf-Pierre, and Shehata (2024). They noted that news consumption can bring up the level of anxiety. They found that people watching climate change news often fear that they might also become a victim of the climate crisis or its associated disasters.

2. Mediatization: The situation described above is also parallel to the mediatization theory. One key aspect of the theory suggests that media serves as a channel for information and also actively shapes how we perceive and interpret the world (Jansson, Bengtsson, Fast, & Lindell, 2020). Media constructs narratives, frames events, and emphasizes certain aspects of reality, which can significantly impact public opinion. Similarly, continuous exposure to media content about climate change can shape people's understanding of its urgency, causes, and consequences, influencing their level of concern or anxiety.

3. Nudge theory: It's a psychological explanation of how certain people choose a response when options are presented in a certain way. In the context of climate anxiety, the **Nudge Theory** guides us on how disaster frames of climate change news push them towards action while minor 'nudges' could be designed to help reduce anxiety and encourage positive action on climate issues (Mirbabaie, Ehnis, Stieglitz, Bunker, & Rose, 2020).

Taking guidelines from the three theories, we are searching the existing literature about what the researchers have found about the effect of climatic news on the mental health of people.

As previously discussed in this chapter and in the context of nudge theory, awareness of climate change can lead to pro-environmental behavior (PEB) when concerns are led to actionable steps (Shantz, 2024). However, framing climate problems as disasters often discourages action and increases passiveness (Lahsen & Ribot, 2021). Shehata, Johansson, and Andersen (2021) emphasized that mainstream media significantly influences how people understand and relate to climate change. Unfortunately, most climate news focuses on disasters rather than solutions (Nawaz, 2024), which can increase fear and anxiety.

Reconsidering cultivation theory, Shehata, Johansson, and Andersen (2021) also noted that mainstream media reporting has significant control over how people understand and

relate to climate change. This is because most people obtain their climate change perception from the news broadcasted and published in media (Maran & Begotti, 2021). This effect of media on triggering eco-anxiety is verified by many researchers such as Loll, Schmatz, von Lonski, Cremer, & Richter, (2023). Research shows that 75% of young people worldwide are scared of climate-related problems (Galway & Field, 2023). In Pakistan, media coverage often gives a disaster frame to climate crisis and rarely focuses on solutions. This leaves people feeling hopeless and anxious over the current situation. We conclude here that the way forward is a solution-oriented approach where we do see climate change as something that needs our urgent attention. However, there is a need to work on presentation attributes of climate change-related news so that the news consumers are motivated towards awareness and action, not towards stress and anxiety.

Research Method

In this research, we have chosen a systematic literature review approach to address our research questions regarding climate anxiety. Systematic literature review (SLR) is a common method to understand the research trends in social sciences. It provides a reliable way to synthesize previous findings and identify gaps in the research (Snyder, 2019). The process of SLR as done by us involves steps: defining research questions, selecting relevant studies based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, and then synthesizing data. We used the PRISMA 27-item checklist to guide us through the steps of systematic review. We have selected and screened articles from online platforms Google Scholar and Taylor Francis.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria of Articles

We included the studies in our systematic literature review article that discussed climate anxiety or similar terms like eco-anxiety. Climate anxiety or eco-anxiety refers to worry about the environmental future. We have selected the studies that explored how climate anxiety occurs and how it appears in different populations. Researches examining the impact of media exposure on climate anxiety were also included. Our main objective was to find the status of climate anxiety in Pakistan, but studies from other regions were also included to provide a better understanding of the situation. The time frame selected for screening studies is from 2020 to date i.e. 2025. The keywords used for searching databases are: Climate anxiety, climate stress, climate depression, and eco-anxiety. We screened the articles based on the titles and abstracts.

Exclusion criteria:

- some articles were related to climate anxiety but their focus was finding the relationship between other nexus of factors such as impacts on policy (N=4), demographic differences within Pakistan (N=1), female gender (N=1), and rural areas specifically (N=1). Such articles were included initially, but as the articles were screened in detail, those were excluded for not being related to our objectives.
- Is a science report or a conference proceeding

Inclusion criteria:

14 articles were eligible for analysis of literature. The inclusion criteria included:

- Mentions the keywords: climate anxiety, eco-anxiety, or climate depression in the title
- Is published from 2020 onwards
- Have properly mentioned methodology

PRISMA Flowchart

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The systematic literature review brought a clear picture of how the research trends may vary across different schools of thought. We have highlighted three prominent variations in the literature.

• **Variation in operationalization: Difference in the perception of Climate Anxiety**

The first and foremost finding of our research is variation in the operationalization of climate anxiety. In the fourteen articles we analyzed, there have been two major trends. One is the clinical use of the term anxiety, and the other is the symbolic use of the same word. Following are sample definitions from our selected articles.

Table 1.1: Indicating Different Perceptions of Climate Anxiety

Clinical use	Non-clinical use
A state of heightened negative emotionality due to a perceived threat from climate change. This construct differs from concepts like climate change worry or concern' (Ogunbode, 2022)	'suffering from eco-paralysis, uncertainty about the future, apathy, loss of control, and powerlessness' (Orrù, Federica Taccini, & Mannarini, 2024)
Climate change anxiety refers to the anticipatory anxiety experienced due to awareness of the threats posed by climate change (Cosh, Williams, Lykins, Bartik, & Tully, 2024)	"Generalized sense that the ecological foundations of existence are in the process of collapse" (Hajek & König, 2022)
a general term for anxiety in relation to the ecological crisis (Pihkala, 2020) Most Cited one	The emerging phenomenon of fear, worry, and apprehension associated with concerns about climate change (Tam, Chan, & Clayton, 2023)

This table shows how the term 'anxiety' refers to clinical symptoms of a medical condition that involves constant fear and worry. On the other hand, the terms anxiety, stress, and depression are also symbolically used to express a state of concern and apprehension.

There is also another trend noticed in the research that new terminology is constantly being introduced in association with climate change. The terms noticed in the sample research are:

Table 1.2: Demonstrating new terminologies being introduced in the literature

Eco-anxiety	Climate anxiety
Climate depression	Climatic Stress
Solastalgia	Environment Education
Climate disasters	Climate Grief

This indicates that there is a communication gap between scientists and journalists (Tran & Nguyen, 2023). Either of them is introducing these terms. As indicated by Table 1.1 each strand of scholars is operationalizing the terms in their context and according to their understanding. There is a need for a unified view of new terms related to climate change. Similarly, there is also a significant communication gap between scientists and the public.

This lack of effective communication hinders the dissemination of scientific knowledge and the understanding of important findings by the general public (Jin Woo Kim & Liu, 2024). Scientists must recognize the importance of bridging this communication gap. If the news organizations talk more about the 'reasons' behind the disaster reports, the

public would be able to relate the effect of the climate crisis to their daily life (Latkin, Dayton, Winiker, Countess, & Zoé Mistrale Hendrickson, 2024).

This variation in understanding of climate anxiety is also linked with the journal and discipline category. As inducted from the selected literature, it appears that climate change and its impact on mental health is an interdisciplinary topic. The impacts of climate change are cross-cutting as it impacts each scope of life. This is the reason our selected articles belong to a variety of disciplines including behavioral, management, environmental, psychological, public health, medical, and sustainability studies, emphasizing the interdisciplinary nature of climate anxiety research.

Variation of countries: Direct or indirect exposure to Climate Crisis

According to my systematic review, I have found two key reasons for climate anxiety: one is the rise of awareness through media (Ogunbode, 2022); the second reason is directly facing the climate disaster (Chen, Bagrodia, Pfeffer, Meli, & Bonanno, 2020). According to Ogunbode., et al (2022), Brazil and Spain had the highest population among the sample population who were worried about climate change.

The team of authors performed a cross-country comparative research and explored that Australia, Chile, Egypt, Finland, Germany, India, Pakistan, Turkey, UAE, Nigeria, Netherlands, Palestine, Philippines, and Uganda had approximately 1/4th of their population concerned about climate changes and had anxiety over the ongoing state. The countries that experience less direct effects of climate-related disasters face lesser climate anxiety; countries such as Norway and Oman and the lowest record of climate anxiety in Russia and Japan. This has something to do with differences in population demographics.

A team of researchers did a systematic review of 12 articles and concluded that different countries' researchers' have been collecting data from dissimilar populations so we can't compare the results without considering the differences in ages, gender, and other demographics. (Boluda-Verdú, Senent-Valero, Casas-Escolano, Matijasevich, & Pastor-Valero, 2022). To prove this, Chen et al., (2020) link the frequency of climate disasters to heightened anxiety.

The study discusses how recurring climate-related disasters, such as floods and hurricanes, can intensify anxiety and stress in affected populations. This study reinforces the argument that the frequency and intensity of climate disasters significantly contribute to climate anxiety, especially in directly impacted communities. We infer here that a nexus of two factors primarily contributes to inducing climate anxiety.

One is disaster-framed climatic news, the other directly facing climatic disasters. While the second case may need medical intervention, the first can be handled by giving a more solution-oriented approach to the news content.

Variation in research approaches: Need for Qualitative Insight

The variation in the results of selected research is also due to the versatility of research approaches. The following pie chart represents the classification of methods among selected studies.

Figure 1.3: showing major approach in research

Boluda-Verdúa & et al., (2022) said that due to differences in method approaches, it is not justified to compare the results of research articles about climate anxiety. Endorsing this, Spano (2022) said that there is a need to have a standard tool to measure climate anxiety. Spano (2022) emphasized using the **HOGG Eco-anxiety** scale as it gave multi-dimensional results instead of only focusing on describing the frequency of anxious individuals. Using the HOGG scale, as opposed to Ogunbode., et al (2022), Boluda-Verdúa & et al., (2022) found in Italy that climate anxiety is on the rise among individuals. However, the results differ among different generations and genders. All 14 research articles followed a quantitative approach. Being a new phenomenon, climate anxiety needs quantitative support to describe it and we can see it already being there. A way forward here is that the topic of climate anxiety needs qualitative insights as well. Moreover, scholars should keep researching climate anxiety so we have a unified view of the general population.

Variety of media role: How Media frames Climate Crisis?

According to Ogunbode., et al (2022), Australia had about 1/4th of its population concerned for climatic conditions. A key factor contributing to the situation here is the framing of climate change by the media. In Australia, for example, Smith (2020) found out that two famous channels in the country framed the protests for climate change differently in opposite frames. One channel portrayed it positively, and the other channel framed it with negative connotations. Similarly, Ogunbode et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive study exploring the correlates of climate anxiety across 32 countries. Their findings suggest that the intensity of climate anxiety is positively associated with exposure to climate-related information and the perceived immediacy of climate risks.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, climate anxiety is a serious issue that affects both mental health and how people engage with environmental issues. While climate anxiety can motivate positive actions (PEB), it also brings stress and fear among the affected. In Pakistan, more attention is needed to understand how climate anxiety impacts people's daily lives and well-being. It is important to address this issue by focusing on local solutions and providing mental health support. Governments should develop policies that tackle environmental challenges by helping people manage the emotional side of climate change.

Our research points towards improving climate change reporting and training our journalists and media personnel to consider the mental impacts of their curated news articles. We interpret this because the findings have proved that media is a key source on which people usually rely for their climate change news consumption.

Meanwhile, as researchers, we should broaden our research to include Pakistan and other victim countries of climate change. More research should be done keeping in mind how to tackle the issue of climate stress. Due to the limitation of time, we couldn't include the previous studies included in systematic reviews. We recommend doing a meta-analysis to reach a unified operationalization of terminologies for better communication between all aspects of society. Ultimately, this research calls for further exploration to better support individuals facing the mental health challenges brought by climate change.

References

- 1) Akram, S., & Mushtaq, S. (2024). Environmental change and floods: the long-ignored effects of displacement on mental health. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1434123>
- 2) Andersen, K., Djerf-Pierre, M., & Shehata, A. (2024). The Scary World Syndrome: News Orientations, Negativity Bias, and the Cultivation of Anxiety. *Mass Communication and Society*, 27(3), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15205436.2023.2297829>
- 3) Anne, Goda Perlaviciute, & Steg, L. (2023). From believing in climate change to adapting to climate change: The role of risk perception and efficacy beliefs. *Risk Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.14193>
- 4) Boluda-Verdú, I., Senent-Valero, M., Casas-Escolano, M., Matijasevich, A., & Pastor-Valero, M. (2022). Fear for the future: Eco-anxiety and health implications, a systematic review. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 84(84), 101904. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2022.101904>
- 5) Budziszewska, M., & Kałwak, W. (2022). Climate depression. Critical analysis of the concept. *Psychiatria Polska*, 56(1), 171–182. <https://doi.org/10.12740/pp/127900>
- 6) Chen, S., Bagrodia, R., Pfeffer, C. C., Meli, L., & Bonanno, G. A. (2020). Anxiety and resilience in the face of natural disasters associated with climate change: A review and methodological critique. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 76, 102297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102297>
- 7) Cianconi, P., Betrò, S., & Janiri, L. (2020). The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health: A Systematic Descriptive Review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11(74), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00074>

- 8) Clayton, S. (2020). Climate anxiety: Psychological Responses to Climate Change. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 74(102263). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102263>
- 9) Clayton, S., & Karazsia, B. T. (2020). Development and validation of a measure of climate change anxiety. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 69(101434), 101434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101434>
- 10) Cosh, S. M., Williams, S. E., Lykins, A. D., Bartik, W., & Tully, P. J. (2024). Detecting and classifying eco-anxiety: development of clinical cut-off scores for the climate change anxiety scale. *BMC Psychology*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-02240-4>
- 11) Dechezleprêtre, A., Fabre, A., Kruse, T., Planterose, B., Sanchez Chico, A., & Stantcheva, S. (2022). Fighting Climate Change: International Attitudes Toward Climate Policies. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4165337>
- 12) Ejaz, W., Muhammad Ittefaq, & Arif, M. (2024). Understanding Influences, Misinformation, and Fact-Checking Concerning Climate-Change Journalism in Pakistan. *Routledge EBooks*, 168–188. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032627526-10>
- 13) Galway, L. P., & Field, E. (2023). Climate emotions and anxiety among young people in Canada: A national survey and call to action. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, 9, 100204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2023.100204>
- 14) Hajek, A., & König, H. H. (2022). Climate anxiety in Germany. *Public Health*, 212, 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2022.09.007>
- 15) Jansson, A., Bengtsson, S., Fast, K., & Lindell, J. (2020). Mediatization from Within: A Plea for Emic Approaches to Media-Related Social Change. *Communication Theory*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ct/qtaa021>
- 16) Lahsen, M., & Ribot, J. (2021). Politics of attributing extreme events and disasters to climate change. *WIREs Climate Change*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.750>
- 17) Lamm, A. E., McCann, R. G. H., & Howe, P. D. (2022). I could but I don't: What does it take to adopt pro-environmental behaviors in the United States? *Energy Research & Social Science*, 93, 102845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102845>
- 18) Lawrance, E. L., Thompson, R., Newberry Le Vay, J., Page, L., & Jennings, N. (2022). The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing: A Narrative Review of Current Evidence, and its Implications. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 34(5), 443–498. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540261.2022.2128725>
- 19) Loll, L., Schmatz, N., von Lonski, L., Cremer, L. D., & Richter, M. H. (2023). The influence of climate crisis-related media reporting on the eco-anxiety of individuals. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 19(2), e2306. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ijese/13044>
- 20) Maran, D. A., & Begotti, T. (2021). Media Exposure to Climate Change, Anxiety, and Efficacy Beliefs in a Sample of Italian University Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(17), 9358. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18179358>
- 21) Mirbabaie, M., Ehnis, C., Stieglitz, S., Bunker, D., & Rose, T. (2020). Digital Nudging in Social Media Disaster Communication. *Information Systems Frontiers*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-020-10062-z>
- 22) Ojala, M., Cunsolo, A., Ogunbode, C. A., & Middleton, J. (2021). Anxiety, Worry, and Grief in a Time of Environmental and Climate Crisis: A Narrative Review. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 46(1), 35–58. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012220-022716>

- 23) Orrù, L., Federica Taccini, & Mannarini, S. (2024). Worry about the Future in the Climate Change Emergency: A Mediation Analysis of the Role of Eco-Anxiety and Emotion Regulation. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(3), 255–255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14030255>
- 24) Pihkala, P. (2020). Eco-Anxiety and Environmental Education. *Sustainability*, 12(23), 10149. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122310149>
- 25) Shantz, R. N. (2024). Mass Media's Potential to Increase Climate Anxiety, Self-Efficacy, and Pro-Environmental Behaviour: A Research Protocol. *Undergraduate Research in Natural and Clinical Science and Technology (URNCSST) Journal*, 8(5), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.26685/urncst.566>
- 26) Shehata, A., Johansson, J., Johansson, B., & Andersen, K. (2021). Climate Change Frame Acceptance and Resistance: Extreme Weather, Consonant News, and Personal Media Orientations. *Mass Communication and Society*, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15205436.2021.1967998>
- 27) Tam, K.-P., Chan, H.-W., & Clayton, S. (2023). Climate change anxiety in China, India, Japan, and the United States. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 87, 101991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.101991>
- 28) Ullah, S., Shafique, M., Khattak, G. A., Shah, A., & Ullah, Y. (2025). An integrated approach for GLOF hazard, vulnerability and risk assessment in the Karakoram Mountain Range of northern Pakistan. *Journal of Mountain Science*, 22(1), 142–155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11629-024-9026-9>
- 29) United Nations. (2023). What Is Climate change? Retrieved from United Nations website: <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-climate-change>
- 30) Whitmarsh, L., Player, L., Jiongco, A., James, M., Williams, M., Marks, E., & Kennedy-Williams, P. (2022). Climate anxiety: What predicts it and how is it related to climate action? *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 83(101866), 101866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2022.101866>